

COMPARATIVE PHYTOCHEMICAL INVESTIGATION OF SOME LAMIACEAE MEMBERS.***S. W. Suradkar, V.S. Undal.**Ghulam Nabi Azad Art's, Comm & Sci College Barshitakli,
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Abstract:

All plants produce chemical compounds as part of their normal metabolic activities. Lamiaceae is medicinally very important family, members of this family are often an aromatic smell. This family is important for fragrance, flavor and medicinal properties. The chemical components in plants have diverse biological roles and are therefore of therapeutic values. Present study deals, quantitative evaluation of *Ocimum sanctum*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Mentha spicata* and *Lionitis nepatifolia* members of Lamiaceae collected from Barshitakli, Dist Akola. (MS) India region with respect to protein, lipid, volatile oil, phenol, chlorophyll and Moisture content was carried out. It is clear from the study that species showed great variation in phytochemical content within family.

Key words:- Phytochemical, lamiaceae, variation**Introduction:**

Medicinal plants have been identified and used throughout human history. Plants have the ability to synthesize a wide variety of chemical compounds that are used to against various diseases. All plants produce chemical compounds as part of their normal metabolic activities. In contrast to synthetic medicines based upon single chemical, many herbal medicines show their advantageous effects through the multiple target sites associated with a physiological process without side effects. So most of the people are consuming herbs as alternate source of medicine to maintain health and improve the quality of life. (Nostro, 2000).

The Lamiaceae or Labiatea is also known as Mint family. They have been traditionally been considered closely related to Verbenaceae (Harley, 2004). Lamiaceae has cosmopolitan distribution and contains 236 genera (Harley, 2004) and 6900 species (Heywood, 2006). Lamiaceae is medicinally very important family; members of this family are often an aromatic smell. The chemical components in plants have diverse biological roles and are therefore of therapeutic values

(Nisa, *et al.*, 2011). Members of this family contains many important bioactive components such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins and other phenolic compounds (Edeoga, *et al.*, 2005). They are also known to have various biological activities such as antimicrobial, antifungal antioxidant. (Word file & Rai *et al.*, 2013). Phytochemicals are the result of plant metabolism. Secondary metabolites are defense mechanism of plant. This family is important for fragrance, flavor and medicinal properties. In connection with this the present study deals with the comparative phytochemical analysis of four members of lamiaceae : *Ocimum sanctum*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Mentha spicata* and *Lionitis nepatifolia*.

Materials and Methods:

For the present investigation four members (*Ocimum sanctum*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Mentha spicata* and *Lionitis nepatifolia*) of Lamiaceae were selected. Plants were collected from uncultivated area of Barshitakli region, Dist. Akola (MS) India. Identification of plants were done with the help of Flora of Marathwada (Naik, 1986) and authenticated by taxonomist.

Fresh leaves were used for different phytochemical tests after washing by distilled water. Standard reagents and chemicals of analytical grade by HiMedia (Mumbai) were used for present investigation.

Protein Content: protein estimation was done by Folin-Lowry method (Lowery, *et al.*, 1951) which is more sensitive method than biuret method. Estimated protein was expressed in percentage (%).

Lipid content: Lipid content was determined by standard protocol of AoAC (AoAC., 1965) and expressed in percentage (%).

Volatile oil content: Fresh leaves of four plants were subjected to hydro-distillation during 2 hrs in an improved Clevenger-type apparatus (Bruneton, 1993 and Clevenger, 1928). Values was expressed in percentage (%)

Total Phenol content: Total phenol estimation was carried out with Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (Malick and Shing, 1980) and expressed in mg per gram (mg/g).

Total Chlorophyll content: Total chlorophyll content was estimated by using 80% acetone for the extraction of pigments. (Sadashivam and Manickam, 1992).

Moisture content: Moisture content was determined by AoAC standard Method (AoAc1970).

Results:

Commonly found phytochemicals in plants are Proteins, Lipids, Volatile oils, Phenols, chlorophylls and water content therefore author decided to undertake preliminary screening of the phytochemicals in leaf extract of four members of lamiaceae namely- *Ocimum sanctum*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Mentha spicata* and *Lionitis nepatifolia*.

Table No.1: Concentration of Phytochemicals in leaf of *Ocimum sanctum*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Mentha spicata* and *Lionitis nepatifolia*.

Sr.No.	Parameter Name of plant	Protein content (%)	Lipid content (%)	Volatile oil content (%)	Total phenol content (mg/g)	Total Chl Content (mg/g)	Moisture content (%)
1.	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	3.25 ±0.1009	5.91 ±0.026	0.65 ±0.0115	0.90 ±0.0437	1.91 ±0.0236	66.38 ±0.3612
2.	<i>Ocimum basilicum</i>	2.53 ±0.0176	5.72 ±0.0865	0.49±0.0088	0.56 ±0.0067	2.78 ±0.0392	51.88 ±0.3510
3.	<i>Mentha spicata</i>	3.68 ±0.0318	3.87 ±0.0333	0.46±0.0153	1.08 ±0.0584	1.94 ±0.0228	82.38 ±0.2173
4.	<i>Leonitis nepatifolia</i>	3.01 ±0.0203	5.50 ±1.2019	0.35±0.0167	0.96 ±0.0291	1.90 ±0.0060	75.32 ±0.2019

The observation signify that, among the four species of Lamiaceae, *Mentha Spicata* shows highest Protein content (3.68%), Total phenol content (1.08 mg/g), Moisture content (82.38 %) and lowest Lipid content (3.87 %). Aroma to the family is due to the presence of Volatile oil and it was found highest (0.65%) in *Ocimum sanctum* and lowest in (0.35%) in *Leonitis nepatifolia*. *Ocimum sanctum* also revealed highest lipid content (5.91%) and lowest moisture content (66.38%).

From the observation it is clear that species show great variation in phytochemical content within family. Similar observation was

made by Obadoni and Ochuko (2001). However, it has been reported that the plant species grown in different geographical areas may contain different phytochemical constituents (Daniel, *et al.*, 2011). Hence a quantitative evaluation of these four members of Lamiaceae from Barshitakli, Dist akola. (MS) India region with respect to protein, lipid, volatile oil, total phenol, total chlorophyll and Moisture content was carried out.

Stastical Analysis: Each experiment was carried out in triplet and data were expressed as mean, ± standard error with mean was also

calculated the formulae of Panse and Sukhatme (1976).

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